

Original Article

Knowledge and Utilization Pattern of Referral Systems among Primary Healthcare Workers in a Community in North-West Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

A functional referral system is vital for the delivery of continuous and effective patient care from primary healthcare to secondary or tertiary level of care. This study assessed knowledge and utilization of referral systems among primary health care workers in Jema'a Local Government Area of Kaduna State. A cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted among 100 primary healthcare workers selected through a multistage sampling technique from five primary health centres in Jema'a. Data were collected on sociodemographic characteristics, knowledge about and pattern of utilization of referral systems. Data was analysed using SPSS version 20 software package. Bivariate analysis was performed and variables with a p value less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant. Most of the respondents (50.6%) had low knowledge, 25.3% had moderate knowledge and 24.1% had high knowledge about referral systems. Referral practices were poor among primary health care workers and common factors identified as affecting referrals were the lack of availability of referral forms and communication networks, the distance of the health facilities from one another and the lack of awareness of the health workers about the referral system. Knowledge about referral systems was relatively low with poor utilization practices of referrals among health workers. Appropriate training programs need to be implemented by local government and state health authorities to enhance health worker knowledge on referrals. Referral materials and communication equipment required for referrals need to be provided to health facilities to enhance the efficient utilization of referral systems.

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INTRODUCTION

Most complicated and life-threatening cases require referral to higher levels of care.¹ A close working relationship between all levels of the health care system is essential in helping patients to receive the best possible care considering urgency, time, cost and geographical factors.² The primary purpose of referral systems is improving the patient care pathway to deliver tangible benefits for

patients.³ A good referral process ensures that patients receive optimal care at the appropriate level and that health facilities are used effectively and efficiently.³ According to the World Health Organization, the components of a referral system include health system issues; an initiating facility; referral practicalities; a receiving facility; and supervision and capacity building which when harmonized will help to ensure a relationship between the different levels of the health system and improve service delivery.⁴ Referral practicalities as a component of the referral system includes the adoption of standardized referral forms to effectively communicate referrals and capture referral data.⁴ Patients ought to be treated with respect and privacy; and confidentiality maintained right from the initiating facility to the receiving facility to ensure a smooth referral process.⁵

Literature has shown that referral systems in developing countries are faced with challenges ranging from poor government policies, lack of synergy between different referral levels, self-referral or bypassing the referral system, paucity of knowledge and attitude of workers on referrals, uncertain clinical/laboratory findings or diagnosis.⁶ In addition, the referral process does not often allow feedback about the referred cases.^{7,8} These challenges of referral systems usually result in inefficiency, wastage of time and resources, and duplication of services.⁹

Primary health care workers play an important role in the referral system by ensuring the prompt referral of emergency cases that cannot be handled at the primary level.¹⁰ The primary health care level is structured to be the entry point into the health care system, thus saddled with the responsibility of providing basic services to meet the essential health needs of the people at the grass-root level.¹¹ It also serves as a link to other levels of care and provides mechanisms for feedback.⁷ Studies in Iran, Zimbabwe and the western parts of Nigeria have

reported on the poor utilization of referral systems among Primary Health Care Workers.^{7,12,13} This study was carried out in a rural community in North-west Nigeria to determine the knowledge and utilization pattern of the referral system among primary health care workers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This was a descriptive cross-sectional study conducted from September to October 2019 in Jema'a local government area (LGA), Kaduna State, Northwest Nigeria. Jema'a LGA is situated in the Lower Savannah plains of Kaduna. Jema'a constitutes an area of 1,661 km² and has a population of 278,735.¹⁴ It has twelve political wards and two tertiary health institutions, a College of Nursing and a School of Health Technology. There is a general hospital and twelve primary health care centres in the LGA. The study population constituted primary health care workers in Jema'a LGA of Kaduna State directly involved in either patient care or records keeping. All primary health care workers in public health facilities in Jema'a LGA who were involved in patient care or record-keeping were included in the study. Those who were employed less than six months prior to the study, those on leave of absence and those not willing to participate were excluded.

The minimum sample size was determined using single population formula ($n = z^2 p(1 - p)/d^2$), where z is the normal standard deviation set at 1.96, with a confidence level specified at 95% and a tolerable margin of error (d) at 5%, considering 10% non-response rate and proportion of health workers with good knowledge of referral systems from a previous study (50%).¹³ The calculated sample size was 100. Primary health care workers were selected through a multistage sampling technique. Five political wards were selected from 12 using simple random sampling. One PHC was selected from each political ward using simple random sampling. From each of

the selected PHCs, 20 respondents were selected by simple random technique to be interviewed.

Data were collected using an interviewer-administered questionnaire adapted from a previous study conducted on this subject matter.⁷ The questionnaire contained information on the sociodemographic characteristics of the respondents, their knowledge and utilization patterns of the referral system and perceived factors influencing their utilization of referral the system. Data were entered into SPSS version 25 for statistical analysis. Descriptive statistical analysis was used to compute frequency and percentages. Tests for associations were carried out using Pearson's chi-square test and Fisher's exact tests where applicable. A p-value set at 0.05 was considered statistically significant. For knowledge questions on referral systems, each correct response was scored 1, while incorrect responses were scored zero. Out of a total score of 12, a score of 0-4 was termed low level of knowledge; 5-8, moderate level of knowledge and 9-12 termed high level of knowledge. Ethical approval was sought from the Research and Ethics Committee of Barau Dikko Teaching Hospital, Kaduna. Permission was sought from the Primary health care coordinator Jema'a LGA and all heads of the selected PHCs. Respondents were assured of strict confidentiality

and anonymity. Informed consent was sought from respondents before commencement of interviews.

RESULTS

Sociodemographic Characteristics of the Study Participants

A total of 100 questionnaires were administered, all the questionnaires were filled giving a response rate of 100%. Most respondents (38.0%) were within the age group 20-30 years, females (64.0%), married

Table 1 Sociodemographic Characteristics of primary health care workers in Jema'a LGA, Kaduna State (N = 100), October 201

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age group (years)		
20-30	38	38.0
31-40	33	33.0
41-50	25	25.0
51-60	4	4.0
Gender		
Male	36	36.0
Female	64	64.0
Tribe		
Hausa	10	10.0
Igbo	8	8.0
Yoruba	3	3.0
Bajju	12	12.0
Kaninkon	15	15.0
Jaba	11	11.0
Fanswam	21	21.0
Mada	4	4.0
Kagoma	14	14.0
Others	2	2.0
Religion		
Christianity	86	86.0
Islam	14	14.0
Marital status		
Single	27	27.0
Married	64	64.0
Divorced	1	1.0
Widowed	8	8.0
Profession		
Nurse	5	5.0
Laboratory scientist	6	6.0
Community Health Officers	24	24.0
Community Health Extension Workers	39	39.0
Health Assistants	18	18.0
Record staff	8	8.0
Work experience (in years)		
0-10	64	64.0
11-20	24	24.0
21-30	11	11.0
31-40	1	1.0
Previous training on referrals		
Yes	76	76.0
No	24	24.0

Table 2: Respondents' knowledge about referral system (N=100)

Variables	Frequency (Yes)	Percentage (%)
Knowledge about the referral system	99	99.0
Definition referral system	87	87.0
Three levels of referral system	73	73.0
Levels of referral are primary, secondary and tertiary	73	73.0
Referrals can occur from lower to a higher level of care	96	96.0
Referrals can occur from higher to lower levels of care	81	81.0
Aware of components of referral system	79	79.0

Table 3: Respondents Awareness and Knowledge of components of referral System

Variables	Frequency (Yes)	Percentage (%)
Aware of components of referral system (n=100)		
Yes	79	79.0
No	21	21.0
Component of referral system (n=79)		
Initiating facility is a component of referral system	75	94.9
Referral practicalities is a component of the referral system	38	48.1
Receiving facility is a component of the referral system	69	87.3
Supervision and capacity building are components of the referral system	50	63.3
Continuous quality improvement is a component of the referral system	45	57.0

Table 4: Respondents' pattern of utilization of referral systems (n=100)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Availability of referral system	97	97.0
Availability of referral forms	95	95.0
Types of referrals		
Written referrals	39	39.0
Verbal referrals	61	61.0
Destinations of referral system usually utilized		
Secondary level of care	88	88.0
Tertiary level of care	10	10.0
Private health facilities	2	2.0
Referring staff *		
Doctor	12	12.0
Nurse/Midwife	44	44.0
CHEW	86	86.0
Referral process*		
Communicating prior referrals	12	12.0
Availability of follow up services for referred patients	19	19.0
Feedback mechanism from the receiving facility concerning referred patients	19	19.0
Accompany patients to the referral centre/facility	18	18.0
Availability of telephone directory for referrals	45	45.0
Availability of functional ambulance(s) for referral	8	8.0
Receiving referrals from other health facilities	53	53.0
Indications (reasons) for the referrals*		
Reduce workload	13	13.0
No bed space	71	71.0
Patient or relative choice	46	46.0
Need for expert management	87	87.0

*Multiple response questions, CHEWCommunity Health Extension Workers

Table 5: Perceived factors influencing utilization of referral systems (n=100)

Variables	Agree		Disagree	
	N	%	N	%
The distance of the health facilities from one another can affect the referral system	87	87	13	13
The availability of referral forms and other communication networks can influence the utilization of referral system	92	92	8	8
The awareness of the health workers about the referral system will go a long way in making its utilization easy	85	85	15	15
Policies of the health facility can affect the referral system	47	47	53	53
Equipping PHCs with referral materials can ease the referral system	91	91	9	9
Patients' decision does not have a role to play in the referral system	40	40	60	60
Family support cannot affect utilization of the referral system	37	37	64	64
Poor knowledge of primary healthcare workers cannot affect the utilization of the referral system	21	21	79	79
Community participation is not important in the referral system	24	24	76	76
Patient financial status is not a factor to be considered in the referral system	27	27	73	73

(64.0%), community health extension workers (CHEWs) (39%), worked for less than 11 years (64%) and reported to have had training on referral systems (76%) (Table 1).

Knowledge of referral systems

Of the 100 respondents, 99.0% said they knew what the referral system was, while 87.0% could correctly define it. Seventy-three per cent of respondents correctly named the three levels of referral systems. A majority of the respondents 96.0% indicated that referrals can occur from a lower to a higher level of care, while 81.0% affirmed that it can occur from a higher level to a lower level of care (Table 2). Overall, 24.1% had a high level of knowledge, 25.3% had moderate levels of knowledge and 50.6% of respondents had low levels of knowledge of referral systems. Most of the respondents (79.0%) said they were aware of the components of the referral system. Of these 94.9% mentioned initiating facility, 48.1% referral practicalities, 87.3% receiving facility, 63.3% supervision and capacity building and 57.0% mentioned continuous quality improvement as components of referral system (Table 3).

Pattern of the utilization of referral systems

Ninety-seven (97.0%) of the respondents said they had a referral system in their healthcare facilities and 95.0% indicated availability of referral forms. Sixty-one per cent of the respondents said they give verbal referrals while 39.0% indicated that they gave written referrals. A majority (88.0%) said they referred patients to the secondary level of care. Referrals were majorly done by CHEWs. With regards to the processes of referrals, 12.0% said they communicate with the receiving facility prior to referrals, 19.0% said they follow up and get feedback from the receiving facilities, 18.0%

Table 6: Associations between Sociodemographic characteristics and level of knowledge of respondents

Variable	Level of knowledge						Test statistic	p-value
	Low N (%)	Moderate N (%)	High N (%)	Low N (%)	Moderate N (%)	High N (%)		
Age								
20-30	18	54.5	9	27.3	6	18.2	F=2.790	0.874
31-40	10	43.5	7	30.4	6	26.1		
41-50	10	50.0	4	20.0	6	30.0		
51-60	2	66.7	0	0.0	1	33.3		
Gender								
Male	13	48.1	7	25.9	7	25.9	$\chi^2=0.116$	0.944
Female	27	51.9	13	25.0	12	23.1		
Tribe								
Hausa	3	50.0	3	50.0	0	0.0	F=19.845	0.237
Igbo	1	16.7	3	50.0	2	33.3		
Yoruba	3	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0		
Bajju	4	36.4	6	54.5	1	9.1		
Kaninkon	5	50.0	3	30.0	2	20.0		
Jaba	5	45.5	1	9.1	5	45.5		
Fanswam	9	56.3	2	12.5	5	31.3		
Mada	3	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0		
Kagoma	6	54.5	1	8.2	3	27.3		
Others	1	50.0	0	0.0	1	50.0		
Religion								
Christianity	33	47.8	17	24.6	19	27.5	F=3.902	0.118
Islam	7	70.0	3	30.0	0	0.0		
Marital status								
Single	12	50.0	7	29.2	5	20.8	F=0.706	0.983
Married	25	50.0	12	24.0	13	26.0		
Widowed	3	60.0	1	20.0	1	20.0		
Divorced	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0		
Profession								
Nurse	1	25.0	1	25.0	2	50.0	F=10.664	0.326
Laboratory scientist	3	60.0	0	0.0	2	40.0		
Community health officer	8	44.4	7	38.9	3	16.7		
Community extension worker	15	45.5	7	21.2	11	33.3		
Health assistant	9	64.3	4	28.6	1	7.1		
Record staff	4	80.0	1	20.0	0	0.0		
Work experience (in years)								
0-10	26	51.0	13	25.5	12	23.5	F=2.626	0.932
11-20	8	42.1	6	31.6	5	26.3		
21-30	5	62.5	1	12.5	2	25.0		
31-40	1	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0		
Previous training on referrals								
Yes	27	45.0	15	25.0	18	30.0	F=5.502	0.066
No	13	68.4	5	26.3	1	5.3		

$\chi^2=Chi\ square\ test\ value, F=Fisher's\ exact\ test, p-value \leq 0.05$

accompanied their patient to the referral centre while 45.0% said they had telephone directory for referrals in their health facilities. Fifty-three per cent of the respondents said they received a referral from other facilities. Eight (8.0%) of the respondents said they had functional ambulances for referrals (Table 4). Ninety-four respondents responded on the frequency with which they

referred patients, of which 59.4% said they occasionally referred patients to higher-level healthcare facilities, 27.1% and 13.5% stated rarely and frequently referred patients to higher-level healthcare facilities respectively.

Perceived factors influencing utilization of referral systems

The commonest factors mentioned by respondents as affecting utilization of referral systems were the availability of referral forms and other communication networks (92%), equipping PHCs with referral materials can ease the referral system (92%), the distance of the health facilities from one another (87%) and awareness of the health workers about referral systems (85%) (Table 5). The study found no associations between the sociodemographic characteristics of respondents and their knowledge about referral systems.

DISCUSSION

The majority of respondents in this study generally had low levels of knowledge about referral systems. Though a majority of the respondents said they were aware of referral systems, a fewer percentage were able to define it correctly and a fewer percentage still were able to mention the different levels of and components of the referral system. Of those that were aware of the components of the referral system, only a few knew referral practicalities as a component of the referral systems. This was similar to findings from a study conducted in Iran.¹⁵ A greater proportion respondents in this study knew that continuous quality improvement and supervision/capacity building are components of referral systems. Majority of the respondents knew that the initiating facility and receiving facility were components of the referral system which was in agreement with the finding from a study conducted in Oyo state, southwestern Nigeria.⁷

Poor awareness and knowledge of referral systems by PHCW can lead to the delivery of uncoordinated and inefficient referral services. There would also be the likely possibility of poor referrals practices when there is a lack of knowledge about the standard protocols for referrals. Offshoots of poor referral practices could include poor documentation and poor identification and triage of cases that need urgent referrals. These invariably would affect the quality of service delivery and ultimately lead to poor patient outcomes.

Regarding the utilization of referral practices among the PHCW, a majority of the respondents admitted that they had referral systems in place in their healthcare facilities. This agreed with findings from a study conducted in Jos, Plateau State, North Central Nigeria.¹⁶ Similarly, a majority of respondents (59.4%) occasionally referred patients to a secondary level of healthcare. This agreed with findings from a study carried out in Oyo State, Southwestern Nigeria.⁷ However, the proportion of respondents who frequently referred patients was much lower (13.5%) in the current study.

A majority of the respondents do not communicate with the receiving facility prior to referring patients, and many of the PHCs did not have functional ambulances for referrals or telephone directories in their facilities. These findings were similar to the study conducted in Oyo State, Southwestern, Nigeria.⁷ Poor documentation and communication referral practices can result in a breach in proper patient care and follow up and ultimately result in negative patient outcomes. The non-availability of ambulances reduces the possibility of effective and prompt referrals from the PHC level. The availability and use of telephone directories can facilitate communication between the different levels of the referral system and enhance the continuity of patient care.

Several factors were identified by the respondents of the study that influence their utilization of referral

systems. Majority of the respondents affirmed that awareness and knowledge of healthcare workers about referral systems could influence their utilization of referral systems. This finding agreed with that of a study conducted in India.¹⁷ Communication networks were also perceived to influence the utilization of the referral system by respondents of this study. This agreed with a study conducted in Ogun State, South-West Nigeria.¹⁸ Furthermore, majority of the respondents affirmed that lack of referral forms influences the utilization of the referral system, which was similar to what was found in a study carried out in Iran.¹⁵ The availability of referral forms and communication networks cannot be overemphasized in the provision of effective referral services. These can affect effective information delivery regarding investigations done, the treatment that is given, the reasons for the referrals and obtaining feedback.

In this study, there were no significant associations found between sociodemographic characteristics and the level of knowledge of respondents, which was consistent with the findings of a similar study carried out in China.¹⁹ However, this was in contrast with a study carried out in Plateau State, North Central Nigeria which showed associations between the level of knowledge and age of respondents.¹⁶ This differences could be attributed to contextual factors in the different settings.

Limitations of the study include the small sample size that may not allow generalization of the findings of this study to other primary healthcare workers in the country. There was a possibility that health workers might have not reported their actual practices as the information provided was self-reported.

CONCLUSION

This study revealed generally low levels of knowledge of referrals and poor utilization practices of referral systems among the PHCWs. The common

factors identified by respondents as influencing referrals were availability of referral forms with other communication networks, the distance of the health facilities from one another and awareness of the health workers about the referral system. There is a need for the Local Government Area (LGA) Department of Health in collaboration with the relevant stakeholders such as Kaduna State Primary Healthcare Development Agency and the State Ministry of Health to organize workshops and seminars for PHCWs on referral systems. Continuous medical education is also important to keep staff updated with knowledge on referral systems. Adequate provision of referral materials such as referral forms, referral registers and referral protocols should be made at the various health care centres by the Local Government Area (LGA) Department of Health in collaboration with the Kaduna State Primary Healthcare Development Agency and the State Ministry of Health. Supportive supervision can also be carried out by the LGA Department of Health to encourage compliance of PHC workers with standard referral protocols. Finally, there is a need for the local and state health authorities to improve communication referral networks by the provision of communication and related equipment for referrals at the various PHCs such as mobile telephones, telephone directories and ambulances for transportation.

Conflicting of interests

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Ethical approval

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